

Safeguarding Biodiversity While Enhancing Productivity in Smallholder Systems: Bridging the Digital Divide with GUARDEN and EWA-BELT

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Executive Summary

Smallholder farmers are custodians of agricultural biodiversity and play a critical role in food security. Yet they face increasing pressures, from land degradation and climate change to limited access to innovation. GUARDEN and EWA-BELT, two pivotal Horizon 2020 projects, demonstrate complementary approaches that aim to boost smallholder productivity while preserving agrobiodiversity, including by leveraging digital tools and data-sharing platforms. This brief synthesizes concrete recommendations for policymakers to amplify these dual benefits across Africa and Europe.

The Challenge: Biodiversity Under Threat, Productivity Under Pressure

Smallholder systems, the pillar of rural livelihoods, are threatened by declining soil fertility, reduced water availability, cropping system simplification, climate change, threatened crop health, and fragmented knowledge flows. Preserving biodiversity is essential not only for ecological resilience but also for sustained agricultural productivity. However, many smallholders lack access to the latest agroecological knowledge and digital decision-support tools that could bridge these goals.

Insights from GUARDEN and EWA-BELT

Biodiversity & Productivity Gains

EWA-BELT highlights the crucial value of using local crop varieties and traditional knowledge, which are often better adapted to local conditions, allowing for greater resilience of agricultural systems to pests, pathogens, and climate variability. Through multi-stakeholder partnerships, the EWA-BELT and GUARDEN projects have enabled the systematic structuring, documentation, and sharing of local knowledge related to seed selection, the production and distribution of biopesticides, or the identification of species with invasive potential, directly supporting land managers and farmers to operate their landscapes and agricultural productions more efficiently. By involving farmers, local managers, researchers, and other stakeholders in participatory processes, both projects foster environments where traditional knowledge and science-validated innovations are openly shared and collectively enriched. This approach not only helps preserve biodiversity and enhance farm productivity but also amplifies benefits across wider communities, increasing resilience and paving the way for sustainable improvements at the landscape level.

Digital Tools & Data Sharing

- ▶ EWA-BELT: Co-developed localized mobile app and community-based data collection systems, which improved early warning of pathogen and pest infestations and optimized prevention and control measures. Digital platforms also accelerated the dissemination of agrobiodiversity management practices among various smallholder farmers.
- ▶ GUARDEN: Co-developed digital mapping tools and dashboards enabling stakeholders to visualize high-resolution species distribution and analyse biodiversity indicators at large spatial scales, and fine resolution.

These diversified approaches could not be possible without access to large-scale open datasets and dedicated IT infrastructures for research and innovation.

Bridging the digital divide: which solutions work?

Both projects highlight that digital tools are most impactful when co-developed with end-users and embedded in trusted local networks. Key findings:

- ▶ **Participatory Design** : Involving field actors and smallholders in tool conception fosters relevance, trust, and uptake.
- ▶ **Open Data & Interoperability** : Using and sharing standardized data (e.g., taxonomic backbones, languages ISO codes, pest and disease common names, including in local languages) across platforms and projects enhances learning and rapid response.
- ▶ **Capacity Building** : Continuous digital literacy training and peer learning (women/youth focus) multiplies adoption, empowerment, and innovation.

Policy Recommendations

Mainstream Digital Agroecological Tools

- ▶ Support transnational investments and Public-Private Partnerships in co-designed digital platforms involving stakeholders engaged in on-the-ground activities.
- ▶ Fund cross-continent partnerships ensuring digital tools evolve based on large diversity of user needs and feedback, shared from an important number of local agroecological realities.
- ▶ Encourage the pooling of IT resources, capitalizing on existing outputs and adapting them to new needs/challenges.

Foster Data Sharing and Interoperability

- ▶ Establish data governance standards that enable secure, ethical, and open sharing of biodiversity and agronomy data.
- ▶ Encourage collaboration between research projects, extension services, private sector and networks of field actors (managers, extensionists and farmers) for evidence-based scaling up.

Protect and Promote local agricultural biodiversity and tacit knowledge

- ▶ Integrate the conservation and sustainable use of local crop varieties and the implementation of traditional farming practices into national agricultural extension programs.
- ▶ Stimulate the protection, mobilization and sharing of knowledge on local biodiversity within which agroecological systems are developed, to deepen our understanding of the existing interactions between agricultural systems and their environment.
- ▶ Provide financial and technical support for participatory on-farm validation trials and farmer seed systems, leveraging digital tracking.

Accelerate Inclusive Capacity Building

- ▶ Invest in digitally enabled training for local managers and farmers, focusing on youth, women, and marginalized groups.
- ▶ Encourage intercontinental multidisciplinary exchanges to share best practices in biodiversity management and digital innovation.

Conclusion

Bridging the digital divide is not an end in itself but a lever to empower field actors and smallholder farmers as champions of biodiversity and productivity. Scaling such integrated approaches, rooted in the grassroots evidence of GUARDEN and EWA-BELT, can accelerate the transformation toward resilient, biodiverse, and food-secure agri-food systems in Africa and Europe.

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